

covalency among these ligands towards coordination to Co^{II} .

Adducts: $\text{L}_2(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgR})_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$, C_2H_5 , $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, C_6H_5 ; $\text{L}=\text{py}$, nia , MeOH): The ir spectral bands due to ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCS} of thiocyanate and ν_{CN} , ν_{CO} and δ_{NCO} of cyanate appear in the ranges corresponding to bridged thiocyanate and nitrogen bonded terminal cyanate groups. These positions are comparable with those of Lewis acids with slight changes due to the change in stereochemistry around Co^{II} . It is also indicated by a negative shift of $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the position of $\nu_{\text{Co-NCS}}$ bands on complex formation. Pyridine and nicotinamide show features of coordination through ring nitrogen and methanol through oxygen of alcoholic group. The presence of $\nu_{\text{Co-L}}$ band in the range $290\text{--}310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ consistent with previous ranges for this mode, supports the coordination of the ligands to Co^{II} . The presence of only one band for $\nu_{\text{Co-L}}$ also suggests the addition of ligands at *trans*-positions of the octahedra¹⁰.

Molar conductance values (Table 1) of these adducts in DMF indicate their non-electrolytic nature. The pink pyridine complex is converted to blue parent Lewis acid on heating at 80° in vacuum indicating coordination of pyridine to Co^{II} . Electronic spectra of all these adducts show the presence of three absorption bands in the ranges $20\,200\text{--}21\,980$, $17\,094\text{--}19\,047$ and $9\,025\text{--}10\,152\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are assigned to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), respectively. These positions, values of spectral parameters, Dq ($911\text{--}1\,410\text{ cm}^{-1}$), B' ($753\text{--}953\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and β ($0.78\text{--}0.98$), magnetic moment ($4.97\text{--}5.18\text{ B.M.}$) and pink colour indicate octahedral geometry (II) around Co^{II} in these complexes.

$\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$, C_2H_5 , $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, C_6H_5 ; $\text{L}=\text{py}$, nia or MeOH
II

Higher values of $\Delta E_{\text{nm}}^\ddagger(\text{Co-L})$ (11.08 for $\text{L}=\text{py}$, 13.23 for $\text{L}=\text{nia}$) compared to those for $\Delta E_{\text{nm}}^\ddagger(\text{Hg-L})$ (5.23 for $\text{L}=\text{py}$, 7.38 for $\text{L}=\text{nia}$), again favour coordination of ligands to Co^{II} . This is also true due to the higher values ($37.52\text{--}42.75$) of $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(\text{Co-Hg})$ obtained on considering ligands attached to Co^{II} compared to ($0.83\text{--}3.12$) for ligands attached to Hg^{II} . Total softness difference values, $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(\text{Co-Hg})$, suggest the following sequence for the stability of thiocyanate bridge, for Lewis acids: $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgCH}_3)_2 < (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 < (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_4\text{H}_9)_2 < (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$. This sequence is also in accordance with the steric effect caused by alkyl

or aryl groups. Stability of nicotinamide adduct is found higher than pyridine adduct due to higher value of $\Delta E_{\text{nm}}^\ddagger(\text{Co-L})$ for the former.

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Formation Constants of Bivalent Transition Metal Complexes with some 1-(3-Phenyl-5-hydroxy-4-isoxazolylazo)-4-sulphonic Acids

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THE azo-dye compounds of sulphonic acid comprising pyridine moiety have gained much prominence as analytical reagents in complexometric titrations^{1,2}. Isoxazoles having arylazo group at position-4 have been reported to possess antidiabetic and agricultural fungicidal activities^{3,4}. Though the formation of a variety of transition metal complexes are well-documented in literature, such studies are lacking with 1-(3-phenyl-5-hydroxy-4-isoxazolylazo)-4-sulphonic acid (PHI-4S) compounds (1). In this paper, we report the formation constants of some bivalent transition metal complexes with PHI-4S.

$\text{R}=\text{H}$, CH_3 , OCH_3 , Br .

1

Experimental

The reagents used are of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. Aqueous solutions of metal nitrates

used for complexation were standardised according to literature procedure⁵. Methanol was further purified according to the reported method⁶. A variety of substituted PHI-4S compounds (Table 1) were synthesised by coupling diazotised sulphaniic acid with 3-phenyl-5- Δ^2 -isoxazolones as reported in our earlier papers^{7,8}.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT DATA OF [M(II)L] CHELATES

$T_L = 2.50 \times 10^{-3}$ (M), $T_M = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M),

$\mu = 0.05$ (M), Temp. 40°.

RPHI-4S R=	ΔpK_a	log K			
		Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
	(A)	Aqueous medium			
Methoxy		4.56	4.01	3.80	3.41
	0.21				
Methyl		4.43	3.97	3.76	3.27
	0.53				
H		4.16	3.93	3.73	2.93
	0.41				
Bromo		3.94	3.82	3.66	2.58
	(B)	40% aqueous methanol			
Methoxy		4.97	4.42	4.21	3.82
	0.27				
Methyl		4.78	4.36	4.17	3.62
	0.45				
H		4.59	4.32	4.13	3.36
	0.73				
Bromo		4.05	3.92	3.77	2.69

Modified method of Calvin-Bjerrum technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti was adopted in potentiometric titrations⁹. Potentiometric studies were performed on a Systronics 335 digital pH-meter in conjunction with glass-calomel electrode. Formation constants evaluated were randomly confirmed by spectrophotometric method¹⁰ and found to be in concordance with each other. pH values were appropriately corrected¹¹ in aquo-organic solvents. Spectrophotometric studies were carried on a Beckman DB spectrophotometer provided with thermostated quartz cells of 1 cm length.

Results and Discussion

The metal-ligand titration curves lie much below the ligand titration curves suggesting complex formation. The absence of polynuclear species in solution has been ensured by adopting the method of Rossotti and Rossotti¹². The absence of metal ion hydrolysis in the pH range of complexation has been verified by the method of Santappa and Ram Murthy¹³. The $\bar{n}$ values were in the range $0.10 < \bar{n} < 0.90$ indicating the formation of only 1:1 complexes with Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II}. Formation constants were evaluated by various computational techniques^{9,14-16} and are presented in Table 1. The log K values correspond to Irving-William order¹⁷. Formation constants remained unaltered to significant extent with the variation of ionic strength indicating that the ligands

react with the metal ion with the liberation of a proton according to the equation¹⁷,

The plots of log K as a function of volume %, of methanol weight %, have been found to be non-linear while the plots of log K as a function of mole-fraction of methanol (n_x) and 1/D are linear. The plot of log K (aqueous MeOH) vs log K (aqueous) was a straight line with a positive intercept¹⁸ equals to ΔpK_a , which refers to the difference in the pK_a values of the ligand in the solvent mixture and pure water. This observation coupled with linearity of the plot log K vs n_x or 1/D plot point out that in high dielectric aqueous media electrostatic forces are important. However, non-electrostatic forces also seem to play an important role in the formation of metal chelates^{20,21} as the dielectric constant of the medium is decreased.

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